

Abstract

This paper presents data on all Cease Trade Orders issued by the British Columbia Securities Commission, with basic descriptive statistics and a discussion. The dataset consists of all CTOs issued since 2000 that are still active as of October 31, 2025. These active CTOs function like a permanent shutdown of the company in terms of the ability to raise equity capital directly in BC. However, many companies subject to CTO in BC are still actively trading stock in secondary markets in the USA and elsewhere. A foreign company subject to the CTO in BC is still active, but what about shareholders in BC who cannot trade? How many such companies are affected by these orders, and what are the economic impacts of the orders?

Keywords: Capital Markets, Law, Halt, Cease Trade Order, Stranded Capital, Government Policy, Failure Rates

JEL Codes:

A1 - General Economics

B4 - Economic Methodology

B5 - Current Heterodox Approaches

C8 - Data Collection and Data Estimation Methodology;
Computer Programs

C81 - Methodology for Collecting, Estimating, and
Organizing Microeconomic Data; Data Access (154)

D2 - Production and Organizations

D22 - Firm Behaviour Empirical Analysis (223)

D6 - Welfare Economics

D62 - Externalities

D8 - Information, Knowledge, and Uncertainty

D82 - Asymmetric and Private Information ; Mechanism
Design

E3 - Prices, Business Fluctuations, and Cycles (2889)

E32 - Business Fluctuations ; Cycles

F6 - Economic Impacts of Globalization

F64 - Environment

G3 - Corporate Finance and Governance

H1 - Structure and Scope of Government

H2 - Taxation, Subsidies, and Revenue

H23 - Externalities ; Redistributive Effects ; Environmental
Taxes and Subsidies
Policies

H57 - Procurement

H8 - Miscellaneous Issues (352)

H82 - Governmental Property

K2 - Regulation and Business Law

K22 - Business and Securities Law

K23 - Regulated Industries and Administrative Law

K4 - Legal Procedure, the Legal System, and Illegal
Behaviour

L5 - Regulation and Industrial Policy

L7 - Industry Studies: Primary Products and Construction

O13 - Agriculture ; Natural Resources ; Energy ;
Environment Other Primary Products

O2 - Development Planning and Policy

P11 - Planning, Coordination, and Reform

P16 - Political Economy

Q3 - Nonrenewable Resources and Conservation

Q32 - Exhaustible Resources and Economic Development

Q33 - Resource Booms

Number of CTOs from BCSC 2000-2025

This paper presents data on all Cease Trade Orders issued by the British Columbia Securities Commission, with basic descriptive statistics and a discussion. The dataset consists of all CTOs issued since 2000 that are still active as of October 31, 2025. These active CTOs function like a permanent shutdown of the company in terms of the ability to raise equity capital directly in BC. However, many companies subject to CTO in BC are still actively trading stock in secondary markets in the USA and elsewhere. A foreign company subject to the CTO in BC is still active, but what about shareholders in BC who cannot trade? How many such companies are affected by these orders, and what are the economic impacts of the orders?

The Cease Trade Order (“CTO”) database is available through SEDAR (2025). This paper lists all CTOs who are still active at companies in BC that were issued since the year 2000, totalling around 2,580 separate CTOs. There is some double-counting of CTO entries when multiple entries for the same company occur on the same day. Also, some companies have multiple CTOs who all remain active. For example, first MCTO and then FFCTO are frequent because a common reason for failure is incomplete financials. Often, a company cannot afford an audit or cannot prepare statements in accordance with audit standards within the time constraints. Continuous disclosure requirements represent the most basic set of responsibilities for companies in BC that are reporting entities. CTOs are only used for “reporting issuers”, which are companies where the number of shareholders is large enough that the company must continue to provide financial details on an ongoing basis as it continues operations.

The database specifies the types of CTO as follows. The main category is a catch-all type of CTO issued by BCSC. It covers things like reciprocal orders, where other provinces make CTOs that BCSC applies here. It also includes all kinds of orders, such as situations where a natural person is an insider of a company who fails to make insider ownership disclosure, and is ordered to cease trading the securities of all companies where he is a reporting insider. This policy is an extreme option that the province uses to target bad actors who undermine the integrity of BC's capital markets. By establishing the rules in a legal framework, the CTO serves as an essential tool for the BCSC to enforce the laws of the road for capital markets in BC.

Table 1: Types of CTOs for types of companies for active CTOs since 2000.

Number of Active CTOs by Type		
..	Public Companies	Non-Public Companies
Cease trade order	1,047	1,080
Management cease trade order (MCTO)	102	52
Failure-to-file Cease Trade Order (FFCTO)	145	102
Total	1,294	1,234

All companies fall into two categories: public and non-public. The public companies were listed on the TSX-V, CSE, or any other exchange in Canada. The non-public companies include several natural persons, many investment issuers, and private companies.

For public companies, the Failure-to-file Cease Trade Order (FFCTO) and Management Cease Trade Order (MCTO) are essential. The MCTO is intended to mitigate damage when insiders cannot trade, but shares continue to trade among arm's-length parties. In a meaningful way, that province doesn't force stranded capital but allows shareholders to trade on new information so that the company can finally meet continuous disclosure requirements. When a company fails, the FFCTO suspends share issuance due to insufficient, timely disclosure of the business's financials. Provinces aim to address situations where shareholders lack minimum information standards. Without timely disclosure, asymmetric information exists in the principal-agent context in which shareholders are the principals and management is the agent. Further information on data definitions in the Canadian Securities Administrators (2012) staff note regarding the database for CTO.

This article breaks down the types of non-public companies as follows. There are a total of 1,237 entities that received CTO status, including 27 individuals (natural persons) and the rest were companies of various kinds. There were around 200 investment issuers, 244 mining companies, 119 energy companies, and over 600 companies that did various things like communications technologies in the 2000s, cannabis in the 2010s, or biotechnology.

Table 2: Types of Entities that are Non-Public Companies:

NON-PUBLIC COMPANIES	
Type of entity	Number of CTOs
..	..
Natural Person	27
Investment Issuer	218
<i>subtotal</i>	245
..	..
Energy	119
Mining	244
Technology	328
Unknown	300
<i>subtotal</i>	991
..	..
Total	1237

This “non-public” category does not include companies that are publicly traded in the USA but were never listed on a Canadian exchange. I don’t know precisely how many companies are private in BC, but how many are public in the USA? I was surprised by how often a company has a CTO in BC, yet its shares continue to trade in the USA or elsewhere. I estimate that 20% of the non-public companies in BC with a CTO are actually publicly listed in the USA now, which raises questions about shareholders' ability to transact in the securities. For comparison, I estimate that +80% of the public companies in this article were also traded in the USA: after a company hired a CTO in BC, most continued to trade there. A minority of those companies halted in the USA after a CTO in BC, but I believe most are still trading actively now. This is an interesting theme for further investigation regarding the efficacy of CTO in BC.

The table and chart below show the number of CTOs over time, by company type. The results separate public and non-public companies to show long-term trends in the number of CTOs across BC capital markets. The results show an average of 1 CTO per week for public companies over the long term. Do some industries get more CTOs than others overall to reflect a greater risk profile? Are there periods when one sector experiences a massive wave of CTO events, indicating an industry shock? Identifying where failures occur is a costly event for BC capital markets when a CTO occurs because this serious government action is the most extreme thing the BCSC can take.

Table 2: descriptive statistics for CTO issued per year by company type.

DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS			
CTO PER YEAR	ALL COMPANIES	PUBLIC COMPANIES	NOT-PUBLIC COMPANIES
Average Per Year	97	50	48
Median	91	48	40
Total	2531	1294	1236
Max	238	136	167
	2009	2009	2009
Min	16	6	9
	2018	2018	2018
Std. Dev.	59	34	33
Kurtosis	-0.1	1.1	6.2

Chart 1: Time Series chart of CTOs issued per year that are still active by company type.

All companies in this study have an active CTO, so they are effectively frozen for equity transactions in BC, leaving local shareholders with stranded capital. Is this an economically significant phenomenon? How does it compare to other countries' frameworks for dealing with delinquent companies?

The data presented here does not measure the total number of companies to compare and estimate the CTO failure rate for all companies in BC, which were approximately 400,000 in 2002 and 500,000 in 2025. The average number of CTOs per year is less than 0.1% of all companies. Note that the entire BC population exceeds 5 million people, so the 27 natural persons with active CTOs represent a small percentage. Reflects how extreme the CTO's policy actions are, as determined by the BCSC.

Discussion

It is possible to extend the exploratory data analysis here by repeating with all “inactive” CTOs. These are situations in which companies fixed problems and were allowed to transact in capital markets again. Search returns 5,909 results for inactive CTO, which is larger than 3,708 total results for active CTO. What patterns in data for inactive CTO? Episodes where clusters of CTOs occurred among companies in a particular business segment? Which companies were able to fix problems and remove the CTO? How to measure the economic impact of CTO policy on companies that are put in “time out” and return to the market? Is it a disciplining factor for management? Does it protect investors?

We can also extend the analysis to look further back into history. Some Canadian jurisdictions have data back to 1971; were there waves of CTO among companies that reflect industry shocks over time? Were these failures driven by exogenous factors in the macroeconomy, or other causative factors endogenous to capital markets like boom-bust cycles?

What are the financial impacts of CTOs? This question is beyond the scope of the current article, but it can be measured in many ways. For example, what is the company's equity on the balance sheet before the CTO occurs? Or the value of equity at another time, like the all-time peak value for total equity on the balance sheet, or peak market capitalization based on secondary-market share prices? Can asset values be included in the measurement of the impact of a CTO? Or even the value of the total liabilities? CTOs can have significant adverse effects on companies across all aspects, and it is vital to think creatively about how to measure the potential economic consequences and the incentives they create.

Note also that companies can continue to operate in BC with a CTO—for example, a mining exploration company with millions of dollars in its bank account can continue to operate. *Shareholders cannot sell, but management can sure spend!* The reason for this flexibility is to allow the company to fix the CTO if they work to prepare the financials, but what if management has an incentive to delay financials while spending money? This is a principal-agent problem between management and shareholders. How can the legal framework be changed to protect shareholders in disaster CTO scenarios? What if the government increased its involvement in companies with a CTO?

To further illustrate the mismatch between BC legal action and foreign governments, a foreign company subject to CTO in BC can remain active elsewhere. For example, a USA-based company that sold shares in BC can be subject to CTO but carry on business elsewhere. What about these investors in BC? Is there such weak coordination between jurisdictions for securities market enforcement, whether within Canada or between provinces and foreign countries? Why would governments subject local investors to CTO when shareholders of the company elsewhere are not?

APPENDIX: DATA FOR CHART 1

TIME SERIES: ACTIVE CTO BY YEAR ISSUED			
YEAR	NOT PUBLIC COMPANIES	PUBLIC COMPANIES	ALL COMPANIES
'00	36	54	90
'01	58	132	190
'02	70	136	206
'03	64	101	165
'04	35	57	92
'05	39	35	74
'06	30	29	59
'07	40	29	69
'08	36	49	85
'09	167	71	238
'10	87	46	133
'11	62	38	100
'12	69	50	119
'13	63	67	130
'14	60	62	122
'15	66	74	140
'16	40	44	84
'17	16	12	28
'18	10	6	16
'19	9	12	22
'20	20	7	27
'21	11	10	21
'22	14	18	32
'23	24	29	53
'24	57	62	119
'25	53	64	117

References

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